

Biochemical Relations Between Helicobacter Pylori Infection and Stressful Biomarkers

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Helicobacter pylori (H. pylori) infection is the most important cause of gastritis, peptic ulcers and the development of gastric cancer. It induces and triggers both local inflammation, of gastric mucosa, and chronic systemic inflammation. It is assumed that these inflammations are caused by extracellular products excreted by H. pylori. The aim of this study was to investigate the possible association between H. pylori infection and the inflammatory response. This study was carried out on 80 helicobacter pylori infected patients, and 20 clinically healthy persons used as control they are classified according to ages which ranged between less than 20 to over 65 years are applied in the experiment .The result of the present study showed an association between serum C-reactive protein (CRP), Interlukin-6 (IL6), Total Protein (TP), Albumin, pyruvate ,lactate ,Complement C3 and Comlement C4. These parameters regarded as predictors or risk factors for Coronary heart diseases (CHD) and ischemic heart disease.

key Words : *H.pylori ,CRP, IL-6, Total protein, Albumin, pyruvate, lactate ,complement C3 and C4.*

Introduction

The H. pylori infected population usually develops chronic gastritis, peptic ulcer, or gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma . WHO has included H. pylori among the category 1 carcinogens, due to evidences that the infection by this pathogen is associated with an increased risk of gastric carcinogenesis .H. pylori infection is associated with gastric hyperchlordria and an increased risk of duodenal ulcer; another subset of its infection can develop corpus gastritis. Both direct bacterial action and host response concur to originate chronic inflammation of the stomach and the pathological outcome in its presence (*Ruggiero et al.,2010*).

Acute H. pylori infection induces mucosal infiltration dominated by neutrophils whereas few weeks, the acute inflammation develops to chronic active inflammation dominated by macrophages,

lymphocytes and plasma cells. (*Andersen et al.,2007*).

CRP is an acute-phase protein originates from the liver. It has been identified as a marker of inflammation used for diagnosis and follow-up of inflammatory diseases . Also it has been considered as independent risk factor for cardiovascular diseases and it is a valuable tool for estimation of at risk persons (*Al-Fawaeir and Zaid., 2013*). There are rises in expression of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1, IL-6, and THF- α . During inflammation, these cytokines are secreted from epithelial and immune cells, thereby promoting concentration of macrophages and neutrophils, and producing inflammation (*Horie and Fujita.,2011*).

An association between lymphocytic gastritis and Helicobacter pylori infection or celiac disease has been found .Lymphocytic giant

fold gastritis is a rare cause for gastrointestinal protein loss. *Madisch et al .,(2004)* as stated by that the H. pylori associated with hypertrophic lymphocytic gastritis, with gastrointestinal protein loss resolved completely following H. pylori eradication .

Shaldoum et al., (2012) demonstrated that the complement system (C) plays an important defensive rule within human body in both innate (natural, non-specific) and acquired (specific) immunity. While Complement component C4 plays a central role in classical and lectin pathways of complement. while C3 is a key protein of the complement system it activated by variety of immunologic reactions such as immune adherence, phagocytosis, antibody response, cytolysis, inflammation, and killing of pathogenic microorganisms.

Glucose is metabolized to pyruvate via glycolysis. Pyruvate is directed to the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA) via acetyl-CoA. The TCA cycle generates NADH, which donates electrons to the mitochondrial electron transport chain so that oxidative phosphorylation can progress. In highly proliferative or tumour cells, the metabolic profile switches from oxidative phosphorylation to aerobic glycolysis, known as the Warburg effect. Mature innate immune cells also rely on glycolysis, although they do not proliferate after activation. The majority of the pyruvate generated by glycolysis is converted to lactate, and glycolytic intermediates build up, meeting the high energy demand of the cell (*Kelly and O'neill.,2015*)

Material and Methods

Patients:

The study taken out on 100- individuals from them 20 healthy person and 80 patients infected with H.pylori, with age range between less than 20 to over 65 years, they came to treatment and follow up in Gamal Abdel naser General Hospital in medicine and endemic medicine departments sustained from continuous (pyloric burning) heart burning and upon analysis them stool samples for the presence of H.pylori antigen they are positive .

and they were classified according to age into four equal groups as follow:

Control group (Group1) consist of 20 clinically healthy individuals with ages ranged from less than 20 to over 65 years. **Group II:** Consisted from 20-infected patients with age less than 20 years. **Group III:** Consisted from 20-infected patients with age ranged from 20-35 years. **Group IV:** Consisted from 20-diseased patients with age ranged from 35 to 50 years. **Group V :** Consisted from 20-diseased patients with age ranged from 50 to 65years. **Group VI:** Consisted from 20-diseased patients with age more than 65 years.

Collection of sample:

Stool samples and venous blood samples of all infected and healthy persons were collected. The Stool samples were analyzed for H.pylori Antigen using ELISA stool antigen test (Golden Bio Technologies Corp H. pylori Antigen ELISA Kit, Upland CA 91786 , U.S.A.)and The collected blood samples were transferred to 5 ml vacutainer tubes, stand about 30 minutes in room temperature, then centrifuged (at 3000 r.p.m for 5 minutes) and all available sera were stored at -20 °C, diluted for biochemical analysis

Biochemical parameters:

Serum CRP (*Price et al .,1987*); IL-6 (*Kishimoto and Hirano 1988*); Total Protein (*Weichselbaum.,1946*);Albumin (*Doumas et al.,1971*); Lactate (*Gutmann and Wahlefeld., 1974*);Pyruvate (*noll.,1988*); C3and C4 (*Muller-Eberhard .,1988*).

Statistical analysis:

The Statistical analysis was carried out using ANOVA with two factors under significance level of 0.05 for the whole results using SPSS (Version 22). Data were treated as complete randomization design according to (*Steel et al., 1997*). Multiple comparisons were carried out applying LSD.

Results and Discussion

The presented data in table (1) revealed that The mean values of serum CRP and IL-6 concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in them was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (1): Effect of Helicobacter pylori infection on serum CRP and serum (IL-6) (mean± S.E.)

Parameter groups	CRP (mg/dl)	IL6 (pg/ml)
G I	2.13 ± 0.29 ^d	7.83 ± 0.49 ^d
G II	3.85 ± 0.31 ^c	10.72 ± 0.93 ^c
G III	3.54 ± 0.37 ^c	16.73 ± 1.18 ^b
G IV	4.29 ± 0.40 ^b	14.37 ± 1.19 ^b
G V	4.68 ± 0.33 ^b	22.07 ± 1.44 ^a
G VI	6.14 ± 0.42 ^a	23.72 ± 1.79 ^a

The presented data in table (2) showed a significant decrease in serum albumin at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant decrease was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant decrease was seen in patients less than 20 years old. The mean values of serum total protein concentration in the infected human groups showed a non significant increase at age less than 20 years old, while showed a significant decrease at the elder ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant decrease was noticed in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant decrease was seen in patients at 35-50 years old.

Table (2): Effect of Helicobacter pylori infection on serum TP and Albumin (mean± S.E.)

Parameter groups	Albumin (g/dl)	TP (g/dl)
G I	4.61 ± 0.29 ^a	7.73 ± 0.26 ^a
G II	4.29 ± 0.21 ^b	7.06 ± 0.38 ^a
G III	3.77 ± 0.27 ^c	7.12 ± 0.34 ^a
G IV	3.85 ± 0.22 ^c	6.98 ± 0.43 ^{ab}
G V	3.91 ± 0.16 ^b	6.37 ± 0.32 ^b
G VI	3.33 ± 0.20 ^d	5.85 ± 0.32 ^c

The presented data in table (3) revealed that The mean values of serum pyruvate and lactate concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in serum pyruvate and lactate in patients at age more than 65 years old, while the lowest significant increase in serum pyruvate was seen in patients at 20-35 years old and the lowest significant increase in serum lactate was seen in patients less than 20 years old.

Table (3): Effect of Helicobacter pylori infection on serum Pyruvate and serum Lactate (mean± S.E.)

Parameter groups	pyruvate (mg/dl)	lactate (mg/dl)
G I	40.68 ± 1.28 ^d	12.46 ± 0.39 ^d
G II	44.80 ± 1.69 ^c	16.35 ± 1.07 ^c
G III	42.97 ± 2.70 ^c	19.46 ± 0.69 ^b
G IV	49.42 ± 2.24 ^c	19.98 ± 1.06 ^b
G V	54.94 ± 3.82 ^b	21.41 ± 1.33 ^b
G VI	65.18 ± 2.35 ^a	29.02 ± 0.56 ^a

The presented data in table (4) revealed that The mean values of serum C3 and C4 concentration in the infected human groups showed a significant increase at different ages in comparison with the recorded values of control healthy group. The highest significant increase in serum C3 and C4 was noticed in patients at age of 35-50 years old, while the lowest significant increase in serum C3 was seen in patients at 50-65 years old. And the lowest significant increase in serum C4 was seen in patients more than 65 years old.

Table (4): Effect of Helicobacter pylori infection on serum C3 and serum C4 (mean± S.E.).

Parameter groups	C3 (mg/dl)	C4 (mg/dl)
G I	140.16 ± 6.98 ^d	24.68 ± 4.03 ^e
G II	191.70 ± 13.74 ^b	43.71 ± 5.87 ^{cd}
G III	196.55 ± 10.69 ^b	66.54 ± 5.46 ^b
G IV	228.21 ± 11.75 ^a	77.97 ± 6.19 ^a
G V	164.30 ± 8.45 ^c	52.44 ± 4.63 ^c
G VI	178.35 ± 10.24 ^c	34.61 ± 3.14 ^d

Discussion

In the present study we examined the association between *H. pylori* infection and serum CRP levels. This significant was came in accordance with the results of (*Al-Fawaeir and Zaid 2013*). CRP levels are known to increase dramatically in response to injury, infection, and inflammation. CRP is mainly classed as an acute marker of inflammation, but research is starting to indicate important roles that CRP plays in inflammation. CRP is the principal downstream mediator of the acute-phase response following an inflammatory event and is primarily synthesized by IL-6-dependent hepatic biosynthesis (*Sproston and Ashworth 2018*).

While *Andreolla et al.*(2016) found no association between CRP serum levels in *H. pylori* infected patients with functional dyspepsia, independently of CagA status; For example, a strong study conducted by *Brenner and cols.*(1999) involving more than 1.800 healthy subjects did not prove the relation between *H. pylori*, bacterial virulence and inflammation markers. Although it was observed an inverse relation between *H. pylori* infection and serum albumin, the bacteria presence was unrelated to C-reactive protein and the leukocyte count, regardless of CagA status. Such result was also reported in several studies that showed no impact of *H. pylori*'s infection in systemic markers of inflammation.

IL-6 is a multifunctional cytokine produced by many types of cells. Inflammation plays a key role in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis that is an underlying cause of coronary heart disease (CHD). CRP is the major acute-phase reactant in humans, which is derived mainly from hepatocytes in response to IL-6 . In addition, some epidemiological investigations have shown a direct association between circulating IL-6 levels and risk or severity of CHD.

Our findings suggest that a strong immune response to *H. pylori* enhanced the systemic inflammation, which was reflected in an increased level of serum IL-6 and serum CRP. With regard to the biological mechanisms for this finding, previous studies have shown that a chronic low-grade inflammatory process leading to atherosclerosis could be one possible mechanism involved in the onset of *H. pylori*-induced ischemic heart disease (*Nakagawa et al.*,2013).

H. pylori may lead to liver injury via specific toxins. In addition, invasion of *H. pylori* in the small bowel mucosa might increase gut

permeability and facilitate the passage of bacterial endotoxins via the portal vein to the liver .*H. pylori* infection causes chronic gastritis and induces a permanent inflammatory response that may increase both the gastric and the systemic indexes of inflammation, such as TNF- α , IL-1, and IL-6 (*Waluga et al.*,2015).

Our results were in line with finding of *Nakagawa et al.* ,(2013), reported that Higher *H. pylori* IgG levels were significantly associated with higher serum IL-6 levels among *H. pylori*-infected individuals while *Murray et al.*(2000) have shown no significant association , a hypothesis was proposed that *H. pylori* infection might play an important role in altering systemic inflammation levels that could be connected to CHD.

our results showed a significant decrease in serum albumin and serum total protein .these results are nearly similar to those reported by *Jalalzadeh et al.*(2010) who revealed markedly decreased total serum protein and decreased serum albumin. *Furuta et al.*(2002) also found that the incidence of hypoproteinaemia was significantly higher in *H. Pylori* positive subjects than in *H. Pylori* negative subjects and was significantly decreased after the eradication of *H. pylori* assumed that impaired acid secretion by *H. pylori* infection might be involved, because the median gastric juice pH of patients with hypoproteinaemia was much higher (4.80) than that of the group with normal protein levels. *Madisch et al.* ,(2004) concluded, that *H. pylori* associated hyper-trophic lymphocytic gastritis has to be considered as a rare cause of protein-losing gastropathy. In these cases, gastrointestinal protein loss may completely resolve solely by *H. pylori* eradication. The significant decrease in serum albumin may be due to impaired liver function by helicobacter pylori endotoxin also The Evidence has shown an association of *Helicobacter pylori* infection with liver dysfunction *Salehi, et al.*(2014) .

The result is showing a significant increase in serum pyruvate and lactate at different ages in comparison with the control group. We can explain this point by the fact that *H. pylori* is a true microaerophile that exhibits oxygen-dependent growth at oxygen levels below 21% arid fails to grow or grows only poorly at the oxygen levels present in air. Thus, the existence of a mixed-acid fermentation pathway in wild-type strains of *H. pylori* may be a manifestation of the metabolic adaptation of the bacterium to its

particular ecological niche .During conditions of high pyruvate accumulation, besides transforming this metabolite via a mixed-acid fermentation pathway, H.pylori may convert pyruvate to lactate using the fermentative lactate dehydrogenase(*Mendz et al.,1994*).

Previous metabolic studies of *H. pylori* have revealed that this bacterium is capable of producing lactate as one of the end products of glucose and pyruvate metabolism (*Iwatani et al.,2014*). Metabolically, lactate can be generated by lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) from pyruvic acid as the end product of glycolysis. However, LDH can also catalyse the reverse reaction, converting lactate into pyruvate. Thus, if exogenous lactate was imported into *H. pylori*, it could be oxidised into pyruvate, which would then enter the tricarboxylic acid cycle. Alternatively, lactate can donate electrons to NADH and, in turn, to the electron transport chain to enhance proton motive force and bacterial energy levels (*Machuca et al.,2017*).

In the otherwise, The Warburg effect is an important concept for understanding metabolic changes occurring in innate immune cells upon activation . Otto Warburg described a metabolic profile of tumors in normoxic conditions, in which glycolysis predominates even though there is oxygen available for oxidative metabolism to proceed. Pyruvate that is produced by the glycolytic pathway, instead of feeding into the tricarboxylic acid (TCA) cycle and subsequent oxidative phosphorylation (OXPHOS), is metabolized to lactate. The Warburg Effect is depicted in. This concept reappeared, but in the innate immune world, in the 1950s, with the discovery that neutrophils depend on aerobic glycolysis for ATP production, and have few mitochondria . Glucose consumption in these cells was high, while oxygen consumption was low. *Newsholme et al.(1987)* investigated macrophage metabolism and showed that most of the glucose consumed by resting macrophages was converted to lactate, with little being used for OXPHOS. Activated macrophages were shown to have increased expression of the glycolytic enzymes hexokinase and glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase, indicating an increase in glycolytic activity in these cells (*Kelly and O'neill 2015*).

H. pylori is complement sensitive and activates the classic pathway even in the absence of specific antibodies. Released cell wall constituents such as lipopolysaccharide (LPSs) can activate

complement and may explain why this bacterium induces gastric pathology without invading the mucosa(*Berstad et al.,2001*).The mechanisms by which the immune response can eradicate gastric Helicobacter infection are unknown. *Ismail et al.(2003)* hypothesized that Helicobacter-induced activation of the complement system could promote both inflammation and eradication of Helicobacter from the stomach. The complement system is one of the natural defence mechanisms that protect the human body from infections and perhaps tumors (*Warner, 1998*).

The present work showed significant increase in serum C4 and C3 this result was came in accordance with the results of *Shaldoum et al (2018)* showing that Activation of C4 is frequently found to be a more sensitive measure of classical pathway of activation due to bacteria activate complement system through delayed inducement of antibody to immune system.

However, *Hussain et al, (2008)* suggested that low C4 levels may falsely be regarded as classical pathway activation (reduced levels of total C4, reduced synthesis or increased catabolism of C4 without corresponding complement activation) and that several other factors may explain low C4 level. While *Dore et al.(2005)* found Lower levels of C3 and/or C4 complement fractions were observed in infected patients with *H.pylori* with respect to controls . Activation of C4 is frequently found to be a more sensitive measure of classical pathway of activation due to bacteria activate complement system through delayed inducement of antibody to immune system.

On the other wise *Jia et al.,(2016)* found that complement component (C)3 and C4 levels remained unchanged. This may be because complement proteins are not directly affected by antigens; they auto regulate and are the most constant mediators in the immune response.

Conclusion

H.pylori infection associated with increased CRP , IL-6,and complement C3 and C4 which are associated with inflammation. Inflammation plays a key role in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis that is an underlying cause of coronary heart disease (CHD), also *H.pylori*-induced ischemic heart disease

References

1. Al-Fawaeir, S., & Zaid, M. B. A. (2013). Serum levels of high-sensitivity C-reactive protein (hs-CRP) in *Helicobacter pylori* infected patients. *American Journal of Physiology, Biochemistry and Pharmacology*, 2(1), 32-36.
2. Andersen, L. P., Holck, S., Kupcinkas, L., Kiudelis, G., Jonaitis, L., Janciauskas, D., ... & Wadström, T. (2007). Gastric inflammatory markers and interleukins in patients with functional dyspepsia treated with astaxanthin. *FEMS Immunology & Medical Microbiology*, 50(2), 244-248.
3. Andreolla, H. F., Sandera, G. B., Mazzoleni, L. E., Tavares, R. G., & Prolla, J. C. (2016). Lack of association between *Helicobacter pylori*'s Virulence And Increased Serum C-reactive Protein Levels In functional Dyspeptic Patients. *Arquivos Degastroenterologia*, 53(1), 49-54.
4. Berstad, A. E., Høgåsen, K., Bukholm, G., Moran, A. P., & Brandtzaeg, P. (2001). Complement activation directly induced by *Helicobacter pylori*. *Gastroenterology*, 120(5), 1108-1116.
5. Brenner, H., Berg, G., Fröhlich, M., Boeing, H., & Koenig, W. (1999). Chronic infection with *Helicobacter pylori* does not provoke major systemic inflammation in healthy adults: results from a large population-based study. *Atherosclerosis*, 147(2), 399-403.
6. Dore, M. P., Fastame, L., Tocco, A., Negrini, R., Delitala, G., & Realdi, G. (2005). Immunity markers in patients with *Helicobacter pylori* infection: effect of eradication. *Helicobacter*, 10(5), 391-397.
7. Doumas, B. T., Watson, W. A., & Biggs, H. G. (1971). Albumin standards and the measurement of serum albumin with bromocresol green. *Clinica chimica acta*, 31(1), 87-96.
8. Furuta, T., Shirai, N., Xiao, F., Takashima, M., & Hanai, H. (2002). Effect of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and its eradication on nutrition. *Alimentary pharmacology & therapeutics*, 16(4), 799-806.
9. Gutmann, I. and Wahlefeld, A.W. (1974) in *Methods of Enzymatic Analysis*, (Bergmeyer, H.U., Ed.) Academic Press Inc., New York, NY, Vol. 3, 1464-1468
10. Hard, G. C. (1970). Some biochemical aspects of the immune macrophage. *British journal of experimental pathology*, 51(1), 97.
11. Horie, M., & Fujita, K. (2011). Toxicity of metal oxides nanoparticles. In *Advances in molecular toxicology* (Vol. 5, pp. 145-178). Elsevier.
12. Hussain N; Jaffery G and Hasnain S (2008): Serum Complement C3 and C4 Levels in Relation to Diagnosis of Lupus Nephritis. *Tropical Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, 7: 1117-1121.
13. Ismail, H. F., Zhang, J., Lynch, R. G., Wang, Y., & Berg, D. J. (2003). Role for complement in development of *Helicobacter*-induced gastritis in interleukin-10-deficient mice. *Infection and immunity*, 71(12), 7140-7148.
14. Iwatani, S., Nagashima, H., Reddy, R., Shiota, S., Graham, D. Y., & Yamaoka, Y. (2014). Identification of the genes that contribute to lactate utilization in *Helicobacter pylori*. *PloS one*, 9(7), e103506.
15. Jalalzadeh, M., Saber, H. R., Vafaeimanesh, J., Mirzamohammadi, F., & Falaknazi, K. (2010). Association of *Helicobacter pylori* infection and serum albumin in patients on hemodialysis. *Iranian journal of kidney diseases*, 4(4), 312.
16. Jia, K., An, L., Wang, F., Shi, L., Ran, X., Wang, X., ... & Chen, J. (2016). Aggravation of *Helicobacter pylori* stomach infections in stressed military

- recruits. *Journal of International Medical Research*, 44(2), 367-376.
17. Kelly, B., & O'Neill, L. A. (2015). Metabolic reprogramming in macrophages and dendritic cells in innate immunity. *Cell research*, 25(7), 771.
 18. Kishimoto, T., & Hirano, T. (1988). A new interleukin with pleiotropic activities. *Bioessays*, 9(1), 11-15.
 19. Lu, L. J., Hao, N. B., Liu, J. J., Li, X., & Wang, R. L. (2018). Correlation between *Helicobacter pylori* Infection and Metabolic Abnormality in General Population: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Gastroenterology research and practice*, 2018.
 20. Machuca, M. A., Johnson, K. S., Liu, Y. C., Steer, D. L., Ottemann, K. M., & Roujeinikova, A. (2017). *Helicobacter pylori* chemoreceptor TlpC mediates chemotaxis to lactate. *Scientific reports*, 7(1), 14089.
 21. Madisch, A., Aust, D., Morgner, A., Grossmann, D., Schmelz, R., Kropp, J., & Mielke, S. (2004). Resolution of gastrointestinal protein loss after *Helicobacter pylori* eradication in a patient with hypertrophic lymphocytic gastritis. *Helicobacter*, 9(6), 629-631.
 22. Mendz, G. L., Hazell, S. L., & van Gorkom, L. (1994). Pyruvate metabolism in *Helicobacter pylori*. *Archives of microbiology*, 162(3), 187-192.
 23. Muller-Eberhard, H. J. (1988). Complement: chemistry and pathways. In *Inflammation: basic principles and clinical correlates* (pp. 21-53). Raven Press New York.
 24. Murray, L. J., Bamford, K. B., Kee, F., McMaster, D., Cambien, F., Dallongeville, J., & Evans, A. (2000). Infection with virulent strains of *Helicobacter pylori* is not associated with ischaemic heart disease: evidence from a population-based case-control study of myocardial infarction. *Atherosclerosis*, 149(2), 379-385.
 25. Nakagawa, H., Tamura, T., Mitsuda, Y., Goto, Y., Kamiya, Y., Kondo, T., ... & Hamajima, N. (2013). Significant association between serum interleukin-6 and *Helicobacter pylori* antibody levels among *H. pylori*-positive Japanese adults. *Mediators of inflammation*, 2013.
 26. Newsholme, P., Gordon, S., & Newsholme, E. A. (1987). Rates of utilization and fates of glucose, glutamine, pyruvate, fatty acids and ketone bodies by mouse macrophages. *Biochemical Journal*, 242(3), 631-636.
 27. Noll, F. (1988). L-(+)-Lactate. "Methods of Enzymatic Analysis" (Bergmeyer, H. U., ed.), 3rd ed., Vol. VI, pp. 582-588, VCH Publishers (UK) Ltd., Cambridge, UK.
 28. Price, C. P., Trull, A. K., Berry, D., & Gorman, E. G. (1987). Development and validation of a particle-enhanced turbidimetric immunoassay for C-reactive protein. *Journal of immunological methods*, 99(2), 205-211.
 29. Ruggiero, P. (2010). *Helicobacter pylori* and inflammation. *Current Pharmaceutical Design*, 16(38), 4225-4236.
 30. Salehi, H., Minakari, M., Yaghoutkar, A., Tabesh, E., Salehi, M., & Mirbagher, L. (2014). The effect of *Helicobacter pylori* eradication on liver enzymes in patients referring with unexplained hypertransaminasemia. *Advanced biomedical research*.
 31. Shaldoum, F. M., & Gobaara, I. M. (2012). Immuno-diagnosis for human infected with *Helicobacter pylori* using C3 and C4. Nature and Science Department of Zoology, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Madinat Nasr, Cairo, Egypt.
 32. Sproston, N. R., & Ashworth, J. J. (2018). Role of C-Reactive Protein at Sites of inflammation and infection. *Frontiers in immunology*, 9.
 33. Steel, R., Torrie, J. and Dickey, D. (1997). *Principles and procedures of Statistics: A*

Biometrical Approach, 3rd ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.

34. Waluga, M., Kukla, M., Żorniak, M., Bacik, A., & Kotulski, R. (2015). From the stomach to other organs: *Helicobacter pylori* and the liver. *World journal of hepatology*, 7(18), 2136.
35. Warner N B M D (1998): The Complement System, Mechanisms of Activation and Use as a Diagnostic Tool, Beckman Coulter, Inc., C-1, pg.10.
36. Weichselbaum, C. T. (1946). An accurate and rapid method for the determination of proteins in small amounts of blood serum and plasma. *American journal of clinical pathology*, 16(3_ts), 40-49.